

PSYCHOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL ANALYSIS OF JUDICIAL EXPERTISE OF MINORS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article provides information on the psychological analysis and social theory of the expertise of juvenile court proceedings in the Republic of Uzbekistan. The principles of judicial examination of minors and the norms of organizing court proceedings based on the rights and obligations established by law are presented. Information such as the study of a criminal case committed by a minor and attention to the analysis conclusion of experts is highlighted. Accordingly, attention should be paid to the behavior, upbringing and psychological state of the teenager.

Key words: Juveniles, psychological examination, forensic examination, psychological analysis, family environment, cognitive state of a teenager.

Introduction

Juvenile psychological expertise is defined as an important tool in ensuring legal protection of the society of the Republic of Uzbekistan and fair treatment of humanity. The purpose of this examination is to assist in obtaining information in a fair manner in juvenile delinquency proceedings. Judicial psychological examination of minors is carried out by experts on the basis of the constitutional legal system. This process is regulated on the basis of the State Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other laws, and is designed to ensure the communication of minors with the court in criminal proceedings. The purpose of this trial court is to ensure justice and fair treatment of humanity. Psychological expertise plays an important role in ensuring freedom, objectivity and legal basis for this purpose. Juvenile psychological examination process begins when crimes and other violations occur. The first task of the expertise is to analyze the mental state of young people, their relationships, and how they have changed in their legal protection and return to humanity. This analysis provides the necessary information for judicial authorities and forensic experts and is of great importance to ensure that the court acts fairly in sentencing. The second task of expertise is to ensure that the court acts fairly and in accordance with mutual laws and legal frameworks. This is a necessary feature in ensuring legal protection and fair treatment of humanity. Psychological expertise provides the necessary information for the court to inform the acceptable and satisfied, and at the same time, it acts as an assistant in the process of making the decision of

the court, legal protection and prevention of falsehoods and ambiguities. It is shown that the third feature of the process of psychological examination of minors in court is to analyze their interactions and social changes during the trial and to take appropriate measures as prescribed by the law. How the court supports them in this process is important in determining their return to society and direction in their social situation. Psychological examination is very important for court experts, members of the court and lawyers of the parties, because at the same time, they can help to provide indicators necessary for their return to society and legal protection.

The main part

The Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates that in order to determine the socio-psychological characteristics of the process of judicial psychological examinations and training for minors, the specialist must study his audience in depth. This not only helps to work together, but also to come up with unique solutions for each teenager, and as a result, each teen understands that they are unique, and can help to boost self-confidence. In such processes, we need to know the social characteristics of the court. The social aspects of conducting forensic-psychological processes of minors are multifaceted and require careful consideration. The family environment plays a major role in shaping the behavior and mental health of a minor. The specialist should evaluate the family situation of adolescents, including family relations, family dynamics, that is, who are the leaders and caregivers in the family, and to what extent there is support or difficulties in the family circle. Understanding the social environment is crucial in determining the factors influencing the psychological state and behavior of minors. For example: Peer relationships are also important during the exam process. Especially teenagers have a strong influence on the condition of their peers. The examiner should examine the adolescent's social interactions, friendships, and potential sources of stress in their respectable group. In addition, social influences such as cultural norms and community expectations contribute to the juvenile's sense of identity and may affect their psychological well-being. The socioeconomic status of the teen cannot be ignored. Economic factors can affect education, health, and overall quality of life. For example, poverty can increase stressors and lead to increased mental health problems. The examiner must consider the socioeconomic context in order to fully understand the juvenile's social circumstances. It is necessary to have information about the psychological characteristics of the court. Psychological features of forensic psychological expertise include a

comprehensive study of mental health, emotional state and cognitive activity of a minor. A variety of psychological assessments and tools are used to gain insight into an adolescent's personality, intelligence, and emotion regulation. A psychological evaluation may include standardized tests, interviews, and observations tailored to the juvenile's age and developmental stage. Trauma and negative childhood memories are important psychological details that require careful examination. Adolescents who have experienced abuse, neglect, or other traumatic events may exhibit unique patterns of behavior and coping mechanisms. Assessing the psychological impact of such experiences is critical to understanding the underlying causes of certain behaviors or mental health problems. Developmental issues are important in evaluating juveniles. Psychological tests should take into account the individual's age-appropriate cognitive and emotional capabilities. Factors such as cognitive development, emotional regulation, understanding and ability to participate in court proceedings should be taken into account during the examination. A mental health disorder, if present, is an important area of psychological assessment. Conditions such as depression, anxiety, attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, or conduct disorder can contribute to a minor's involvement in legal matters. The examiner works to identify these conditions and recommend appropriate measures or treatment. In the last part of the article, the ability of the psychological expertise of the juvenile court to ensure legal protection and fair treatment of humanity in the society of the Republic of Uzbekistan is determined. Studying about the Constitution and other laws, carrying out examinations in the processes of crime and their results will help to ensure justice and fair treatment of humanity in the society of the Republic of Uzbekistan. In the section of suggestions, based on the ideas presented in the article, it is necessary to present proposals aimed at strengthening the system of expertise and ensuring its objectivity, what reforms should be implemented in the next stages for the development of judicial psychological expertise for minors. This plays an important role in ensuring a more fair and transparent, impartial execution of the court process.

Conclusion

It is of great importance that the psychological expertise of the Republic of Uzbekistan in providing social and legal protection to minors, the fact that it reflected in the prevention of crime and officialdom, and was an assistant in the return to society. This, together with the legal system and judicial organizations, to develop the expertise process, to acquire more knowledge about the state,

society, and legal consequences, to master and study the laws well, in order to make the system more fair and objective.

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